

Complex Formation in Molten Salts : Thermodynamics of Association Equilibria of Single and Mixed Ligand Complexes : A Review[†]

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Study of association equilibria involving metal ion with single and mixed ligand in molten salts by EMF and computer methods is reviewed. Temperature coefficients of the association constants have been evaluated and applicability of quasi-lattice formulation examined.

THERMODYNAMICS of association equilibria in molten salts have been studied by several techniques as polarography, chronopotentiometry, spectroscopy, solubility etc.; due to simplicity of technique, high degree of reproducibility and precision which can enable extrapolation and computer evaluation of data, EMF method has been widely used. The measurements in a molten salt electrochemical cell involve essentially the same considerations¹ as in an analogous aqueous cell, viz., the need for a reversible, responsive indicator and reference electrodes which would be stable at the temperature employed and in the corrosive environment imposed by the solvent and the need for boundary between solutions of different compositions. In this paper, studies on association equilibria involving single and mixed ligand complexes of metals as silver, thallium, cadmium, lead, cobalt etc. with halides, nitrite, cyanide, phosphate, sulphate, chromate, molybdate, iodate in single alkali and alkaline earth metal nitrates, sulphates and halides and their charge symmetric (solvents with equal number of cations and anions) and asymmetric (solvents with different number of cations and anions) mixtures are reviewed. The choice of the solvent systems is governed by considerations of melting point, thermal stability, ion-reactivity with electrodes and containers and non-hygroscopic and non-complexing nature of the components².

Molten Salt Electrochemical Cells

Studies have been carried out using the concentration cells with metal-metal ion (reversible to metal ion, cell A or through the solubility equilibrium of two metal oxides, cell C) and metal-insoluble metal halide (reversible to halide ion, cell B) as indicator electrodes. The electrode reactions, equations for Nernst slope and activity coefficients are summarized in Table 1. Detailed description of cells, experimental technique, pretreatment of

electrodes, solvent preparation etc. has been given³⁻¹⁰. The liquid junction potential has been considered to be negligible since the solutions are dilute and the same solvent is used on both sides of the junction.

Behaviour of reversible solid and liquid metal-metal ion as indicator electrode in halide and nitrate melts have been reported¹¹⁻¹⁷. One of the factors that favours the reversibility of the metal-metal ion electrode in molten salts is the increased rate of oxidation-reduction at the electrode surface giving rise to a large exchange current and a thermodynamically "well-behaved" electrode¹². A disadvantage could arise¹⁸⁻²⁰ if the metal is easily oxidised. Ag/Ag⁺ electrode which has been extensively used as the indicator electrode, has been shown to be reversible¹⁴, and since the oxides are easily volatilised from the surface below c 250°, the surface is free from oxide impurities.

Ag-AgX(s), X⁻ (X=Cl, Br, I) electrode has been used²¹ as electrode of second kind (cell B). Since the concentration of the metal ion is controlled through the solubility equilibrium of silver halide, it is effectively an anion-responsive electrode. Use of Ag-AgCl(s) electrode as indicator is precluded above c 250° due to relatively higher solubility of silver chloride in molten nitrates; Ag⁺ from the solubility equilibrium may then compete with complexing metal ions, complicating analysis of data⁹.

Use of electrode of third kind (cell C), Pd-PdO-MO (e.g., M=Cd, Pb) in molten nitrates, responsive to M²⁺ through the solubility equilibria of two insoluble oxides, was first suggested by Inman²².

Reference electrodes generally used¹² are Ag-Ag⁺ and Ag-AgX(s), isolated in a portion of the melt; electrical contact with the solvent is made

[†] Dedicated to Professor R. C. Mehrotra, F. N. A. (Former Vice-Chancellor, University of Delhi, Delhi) on his sixtieth birthday.

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TABLE I - ELECTRODE REACTIONS, EQUATIONS FOR NERNST SLOPES AND ACTIVITY COEFFICIENTS FOR ELECTROCHEMICAL CELLS USED IN THE STUDY OF ASSOCIATION EQUILIBRIA

Cell	Electrode reaction and Nernst equation	Equation for Activity Coefficient (in presence of complexing ion)
<p>Cell A</p> $\text{Ag, Ag}^+ \left \begin{array}{c} \text{Solvent} \\ \text{AgNO}_3 \\ (R'_{Ag}) \end{array} \right \left \begin{array}{c} \text{Solvent} \\ \text{AgNO}_3, L^- \\ (R_{Ag}, R_L) \end{array} \right \text{Ag}^+, \text{Ag}$	$\text{Ag} = \text{Ag}^+ + e^-$ $E_{\text{cell}} = \frac{2.303 RT}{F} \log \frac{R_{Ag}}{R'_{Ag}}$	$\Delta E^{\dagger}_{\text{cell}} = \frac{2.303 RT}{F} \log R_{Ag} - \frac{RT}{F} N_L$ <p>Second term on the right hand side arising as a result of dilution, is small and has generally been neglected.</p>
<p>Cell B</p> $\text{Ag, AgX(s)} \left \begin{array}{c} \text{Solvent} \\ \text{AgX(s), X} \\ (R'_X) \end{array} \right \left \begin{array}{c} \text{Solvent} \\ \text{M(NO}_3)_m, \text{X} \\ (R_M, R_X) \end{array} \right \text{AgX(s), Ag}$	$\text{Ag} + \text{X}^- = \text{AgX(s)} + e^-$ $E_{\text{cell}} = \frac{2.303 RT}{F} \log \frac{R_X}{R'_X}$	<p>M^{m+} added as $M(\text{NO}_3)_m$</p> $\gamma_{M^{m+}}^{-1} = \exp \left(\frac{\Delta E^{\dagger}_{\text{cell}} F}{RT} \right)$ <p>M^{m+} added as MX_m</p> $\gamma_{M^{m+}}^{-1} = \left[\frac{R_X + R_{MX_m}}{R_X} \right] \exp \left(\frac{\Delta E^{\dagger}_{\text{cell}} F}{RT} \right)$
<p>Cell C</p> $\text{Ag, AgX(s)} \left \begin{array}{c} \text{Solvent} \\ \text{AgX(s), X} \\ (R'_X) \end{array} \right \left \begin{array}{c} \text{Solvent} \\ \text{Cd}^{2+}/\text{Pb}^{2+}, \text{X} \\ (\text{RCd}^{2+}/\text{Pb}^{2+}, R_X) \end{array} \right \left \begin{array}{c} \text{Pd, PdO,} \\ \text{CdO/PbO} \end{array} \right \text{Pd} = \text{Pd}^{2+} + 2e^-$ <p>$(M = \text{Ti}^+, \text{Cd}^{2+}, \text{Zn}^{2+}, \text{Pb}^{2+}$ etc., L is ligand (inclusive of $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$)</p>	$\text{CdO/PbO} + \text{Pd}^{2+} = \text{PdO} + \text{Cd}^{2+}/\text{Pb}^{2+}$ $\text{CdO/PbO} + \text{Pd} = \text{PdO} + \text{Cd}^{2+}/\text{Pb}^{2+} + 2e^-$ $E_{\text{cell}} = \text{Constant} + \frac{2.303 RT}{2F} \log R_{Cd/Pb}$	$\log \gamma_{\text{Cd/Pb}} = \frac{\Delta E^{\dagger}_{\text{cell}} F}{S_{\text{expt}}}$ <p>S_{expt} is experimental Nernst slope.</p>

† R, T, F have the usual thermodynamic significance, ΔE_{cell} is the difference in emf of the cell in presence and absence of complexing ion.

Prime (') represents concentration units in reference half-cell.

through a fine porosity fritted glass disc or an asbestos fibre sealed through a glass diaphragm.

The choice of the concentration units and standard states for a solution depends upon the model employed for the interpretation of solution properties; in molten salts Temkin model²³ has been widely used. For a system containing metal (M^{m+}) and ligand (L^{l-}) ions in the reciprocal charge symmetric ($\text{AC}+\text{BC}$) or asymmetric ($\text{AC}+\text{B}'\text{C}_2$) systems, mol fraction (N_i) of M^{m+} and L^{l-} in terms of mol ratios (R_i , mol of solute per mol of solvent) are¹⁰

$$N_M^{m+} = \frac{n_M^{m+}}{\sum n_{\text{cations}}} = \frac{R_{M(\text{NO}_3)_m}}{1 + \left(\frac{1}{p}\right) R_{A_1L} + R_{M(\text{NO}_3)_m}} \dots (1)$$

$$N_L^{l-} = \frac{n_L^{l-}}{\sum n_{\text{anions}}} = \frac{R_{A_1L}}{1 + mp R_{M(\text{NO}_3)_m} + R_{A_1L}}$$

where n_i is the number of mols of the species i ; $p=1$ for the solvent ($\text{AC}+\text{BC}$), and $p=(y+1)/(y+2)$ for the solvent ($\text{AC}+\text{B}'\text{C}_2$), y being the ratio of mols of univalent solvent cations and divalent solvent cations. At $R_i < 10^{-3}$, as is generally employed in these investigations, ion mol ratios are not significantly different from the mol fractions.

Although solutes are generally added as $M(\text{NO}_3)_m$ and A_1L , their mol ratios, $< 10^{-3}$, do not significantly alter the ratio of two solvent cations.

Evaluation of Association Constants

Single ligand complexes: Negative deviations from Henry's law in presence of complexing ions have been interpreted due to the formation of associated or complexed species in solution. Thermodynamic association constants and related parameters in molten salts from EMF data have generally been evaluated using the graphical extrapolation method of Braunstein *et al*⁴; computer evaluation method has been employed by Inman *et al*²⁴ and others²⁵⁻²⁸.

Consider a dilute solution containing both M^{m+} and L^{l-} in molten salt mixture ($\text{AC}+\text{BC}$) or ($\text{AC}+\text{B}'\text{C}_2$) as solvent, and assume that M^{m+} and L^{l-} associate to form the species of the type $\text{ML}^{(m-l)+}$, $\text{ML}_2^{(m-2l)+}$, $\text{M}_2\text{L}^{(2m-l)+}$ etc. for which corresponding association constants K_{11} , K_{12} , K_{21} etc. are defined by equations,

where the concentrations may be expressed as mol ratios. Expressing the total (stoichiometric) concentrations of the solute components* in the solvent by the mass-balance equations^{4,22}:

$$R_M = R_M^{m+} + R_{ML}^{(m-1)+} + R_{ML_2}^{(m-2)+} + 2R_{M_2L}^{(2m-1)+} + \dots \quad (3)$$

$$R_L = R_L^{l-} + pR_{ML}^{(m-1)+} + 2pR_{ML_2}^{(m-2)+} + pR_{M_2L}^{(2m-1)+} + \dots \quad (4)$$

and defining the activity coefficients of the solutes by equations

$$1/\gamma_M = R_M/R_M^{m+}$$

$$1/\gamma_{SL} = R_L/R_L^{l-}$$

equations for activity coefficients in terms of K_{ij} and R_i are:

$$1/\gamma_M = 1 + K_{11}R_L + K_{11}(2K_{21} - pK_{11})R_LR_M + K_{11}K_{12}R_L^2 + \dots \quad (5)$$

$$\ln 1/\gamma_M = K_{11}R_L + K_{11}(2K_{21} - pK_{11})R_LR_M + K_{11}(K_{12} - \frac{1}{2}K_{11})R_L^2 + \dots \quad (6)$$

$$1/\gamma_{SL} = 1 + pK_{11}R_M + pK_{11}(2K_{12} - K_{11})R_LR_M + pK_{11}K_{21}R_M^2 + \dots \quad (7)$$

Association constants using Ag-Ag⁺ (cell A) or Pd-PdO-CdO/PbO (cell C) indicator electrodes may be evaluated from the relationships based on equation (6), viz.,

$$S_M(0,0) = \lim_{R_M \rightarrow 0} [S_M(0)] = \lim_{\substack{R_L \rightarrow 0 \\ R_M \rightarrow 0}} \left[\frac{\partial \ln(1/\gamma_M)}{\partial R_L} \right]_{R_M} = K_{11} \quad (8)$$

$$\lim_{\substack{R_M \rightarrow 0 \\ R_L \rightarrow 0}} \left[\frac{\partial (1 + K_{11}R_M)S_M(0)}{\partial R_M} \right] = 2K_{11}K_{21} \quad (9)$$

$$\ln(1/\gamma_M) = AR_L + BR_L^2 + \dots \quad (10)$$

$$\lim_{R_M \rightarrow 0} [B] = [B_0] = K_{11}(K_{12} - \frac{1}{2}K_{11}) \quad (11)$$

For the cell B, using Ag-AgX(s) as indicator electrode, the corresponding equations are

$$S_L(0,0) = \lim_{R_L \rightarrow 0} [S_L(0)] = \lim_{\substack{R_L \rightarrow 0 \\ R_M \rightarrow 0}} \left[\frac{\partial (1/\gamma_{SL})}{\partial R_M} \right]_{R_L} = pK_{11} \quad (12)$$

$$\lim_{\substack{R_L \rightarrow 0 \\ R_M \rightarrow 0}} \left[\frac{\partial S_L(0)}{\partial R_L} \right] = \lim_{R_L \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\partial^2 (1/\gamma_{SL})}{\partial R_L \partial R_M} \right] = pK_{11}(2K_{12} - K_{11}) \quad (13)$$

$$(1/\gamma_{SL} - 1) = AR_M + BR_M^2 + \dots \quad (14)$$

$$\lim_{R_L \rightarrow 0} [B] = [B_0] = pK_{11}K_{21} \quad (15)$$

Since functions are extrapolated to zero concentration both in respect of R_M and R_L , association constants are truly thermodynamic parameters.

Limiting slopes $S_M(0)$ or $S_L(0)$ are generally obtained from large scale plots of $\ln(1/\gamma_M)/(1/\gamma_{SL})$ vs R_L/R_M which are rectilinear at low R_L . For such systems (cf. eqn. 7)

$$\lim_{R_L \rightarrow 0} 1/\gamma_{SL} = 1 + pK_{11}R_M \quad (16)$$

$$\text{or } \ln(1/\gamma_{SL}) = \ln(1 + pK_{11}R_M) \quad (17)$$

from which one has

$$\left[\frac{\partial \ln(1/\gamma_{SL})}{\partial R_M} \right]_{R_M} = \frac{pK_{11}}{1 + pK_{11}R_M} \quad (18)$$

using the thermodynamic relationship,

$$\lim_{R_L \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\partial \ln(1/\gamma_M)}{\partial R_L} \right]_{R_M} = \lim_{R_M \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\partial \ln(1/\gamma_{SL})}{\partial R_M} \right]_{R_M} = S_M(0) \quad (19)$$

it also follows that

$$S_M(0) = \frac{pK_{11}}{1 + pK_{11}R_M} \quad (20)$$

Equation (20), valid at low solute concentrations, enables evaluation of K_{11} from a single limiting data for a single initial R_M . Values of K_{11} thus evaluated have been reported^{7,10,20} to be close to those from the extrapolated data at several initial R_M .

Mixed ligand complexes: These studies have been reported^{5,21,22} for mixed silver halides in molten nitrates. Considering the example of chloride-bromide complexes and representing the association constants for single chloride and bromide species (AgX , AgX_2^- and Ag_2X^+) by K_{11} , K_{12} and K_{21} , and K_{11}^* , K_{12}^* and K_{21}^* respectively, β , the mixed association constants for $AgClBr^-$ (at fixed R_{Cl} and varying R_{Br} and vice versa) defined by

$$\beta = R_{AgClBr^-} / R_{Ag^+} \cdot R_{Cl^-} \cdot R_{Br^-} \quad (21)$$

may be evaluated from the equation^{5,21}

$$\lim_{R_{Cl} \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\partial S_{Ag}(0, Cl, 0)}{\partial R_{Cl}} \right] = \lim_{R_{Br} \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\partial S_{Ag}(0, 0, Br)}{\partial R_{Br}} \right] = (\beta - \beta_{11} \beta_{11}^*) / 2.303 \quad (22)$$

*Subscripts M, L and SL refer to components $M(NO_3)_n$, A_1L and $(A, B \text{ or } B')L$ respectively.

where $\beta_{11}(=K_{11})$ and $\beta_{11}^*(=K_{11}^*)$ are given by

$$S_{Ag}(0,0,0) = \lim \left[\frac{\partial \ln(1/\gamma_{Ag})}{\partial R_{Cl}} \right] = \beta_{11} \quad \dots (23)$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{Fixed Br } R_{Ag} \rightarrow 0 \\ R_{Cl} \rightarrow 0 \\ R_{Br} \rightarrow 0 \end{array} \quad R_{Ag}, R_{Br}$$

$$S_{Ag}(0,0,0) = \lim \left[\frac{\partial \ln(1/\gamma_{Ag})}{\partial R_{Br}} \right] = \beta_{11}^* \quad \dots (24)$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{Fixed Cl } R_{Ag} \rightarrow 0 \\ R_{Br} \rightarrow 0 \\ R_{Cl} \rightarrow 0 \end{array} \quad R_{Ag}, R_{Cl}$$

Use of digital computer for evaluating association constants from potentiometric data have been reported²⁴⁻²⁸. It involves several cycles of Newton-Raphson iterative procedure involving ligand-balance equations in least-squares curve-fitting in conjunction with metal-balance equation.

Results and Discussion

Reversible behaviour of different types of indicator electrodes in cells (A) to (C) has been demonstrated (Fig. 1). In view of discrepancy between calculated and observed Nernst slopes with Pd-PdO-CdO/PbO electrode (cell C), considered²² to

Fig. 1. E.M.F. vs R_M/R_X in $KNO_3-Ba(NO_3)_2$. ● (Experimental), — (Theoretical), I (Ag-Ag⁺), II [Ag-AgBr(s)], III [Ag-AgI(s)], IV (Pd-PdO-CdO), V (Pd-PdO-PbO).

arise due to mixed potential at the electrode surface, experimental slope (S_{expt}), was employed^{7,10,25,30,33} instead of that from the Nernst equation $\left(\frac{2.303 RT}{2F} \right)$ in the evaluation of

γ_M . In a typical case (Table 2), γ_{Br} (X=Br, I) obtained from CdX_2 addition are consistent^{24,25} with the values obtained from $Cd(NO_3)_2$ addition. This establishes usefulness of the latter, where anhydrous solute is difficult to prepare. Typical plots using the extrapolation procedure of Braunsstein *et al* are given in Fig. 2. Values of K_{11} ($ML^{(m-1)+}$) and β ($AgClBr^-$) for various systems in different solvents are summarised in Table 3. Data for K_{11} for the same system with different indicator

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF INTERPOLATED VALUE OF γ_{Br}^{-1} OBTAINED FROM CdX_2 (X=Br, I) AND $Cd(NO_3)_2$ ADDITION

$R_{Cd} a^{2+} \times 10^3$	γ_{Br}^{-1} CdX ₂ addition	Cd(NO ₃) ₂ addition
(Solvent : NaNO ₃ -KNO ₃ (1 : 1), Temp. = 513.2 K, X=Br, $R_{Br} = 1.732 \times 10^{-2}$, Ref. 34)		
0.1195	1.109	1.109
0.2845	1.270	1.268
0.6940	1.687	1.687
0.7655	1.820	1.779
(Solvent : KNO ₃ -Ba(NO ₃) ₂ (0.876 : 0.124), Temp. = 568.2 K, X=I, $R_I = 9.829 \times 10^{-2}$, Ref. 35)		
0.2499	1.050	1.048
0.7080	1.120	1.110
1.1326	1.220	1.190
1.7319	1.330	1.320

electrodes illustrated for Cd-Br complexes (Fig. 2a) are consistent^{7,30}. Also, K_{11} from a single set data (eqn. 20) are seen^{7,10,30} (Fig. 2b) to be close to those from extrapolation data (eqn. 8) at several initial solute concentrations. A comparison of association constants for Ag-X (X=Cl, Br) complexes in NaNO₃-Ba(NO₃)₂ from graphical extrapolation and computer evaluation (using one degree fit) for K_{11} is shown in Table 4. The stoichiometric association constants K_{11} are generally comparable. Since several cycles have to be used, the error introduced in evaluating association constants may get accumulated in the higher ones due to which the utility of computer method in evaluating higher association constants is limited. A possible modification would be simultaneous processing of data at various initial solute concentration over a wide range of concentrations.

Fig. 2. (a) Graphical extrapolation of limiting slopes obtained with Ag, AgBr(s), (O) (Eqn. 12) and Pd-PdO-CdO, (●) (Eqn. 8) electrodes to evaluate K_{11} at 568.2 K. (b) Graphical extrapolation of limiting slopes to evaluate K_{11} ($PbCl^+$ at 588.2 K using equations 8 (O) and 20 (Δ)).

Applicability of quasi-lattice model: From the temperature-dependence of the association constants, specific Helmholtz free energies (ΔA_{ij}), the energy required for the formation of the associated species

TABLE 3—ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS K_{11} AND SPECIFIC HELMHOLTZ FREE ENERGIES $-\Delta A_{11}$ FOR REACTION $M^{m+} + L^l- \rightleftharpoons ML^{(m-l)+}$ IN MOLTEN SALTS*

Complex/Solvent (Composition, Mol %)	Temp. range K	Cell used	K_{11}	$-\Delta A_{11}$	Reference
<i>Silver-Chloride</i>					
NaNO ₃ (100)	(604–711)	A	227–146	20.3±0.1	38
KNO ₃ (100)	623, 709	A	553, 315	24.4±0.1	56
	643, 709	A	415, 270	23.7±0.1	36
	658	A	455	24.7	51
	675, 696	A	330, 290	23.6	57
CsNO ₃ (100)	713	A	506	27.4	55
LiNO ₃ –KNO ₃ (47 : 53)	498	A	860	21.3	58
	664	A	380	24.0	55
	513	A	1090	23.0	59
NaNO ₃ –KNO ₃ (50 : 50)	(506–801)	A	1050–133	22.4±0.3	51
KNO ₃ –CsNO ₃ (67 : 33)	658	A	530	25.6	55
KNO ₃ –Ca(NO ₃) ₂ (80 : 20)	593, 623	A	518, 417	22.9±0.1	47
KNO ₃ –Sr(NO ₃) ₂ (80 : 20)	623	A	336	21.9	47
KNO ₃ –Ba(NO ₃) ₂ (89 : 11)	(623–663)	A	396–288	22.4±0.3	60
NaNO ₃ –Ba(NO ₃) ₂ (94.2 : 5.8)	(623–673)	A	290–207	21.1±0.1	61
Li ₂ SO ₄ –K ₂ SO ₄ (71.5 : 28.5)	(600–700)	A	32–27	9.8±1.2	62
<i>Silver-Bromide</i>					
NaNO ₃ (100)	(675–773)	A	633–352	27.3±0.1	49
KNO ₃ (100)	(676–773)	A	932–540	29.8±0.4	63
KNO ₃ –Ba(NO ₃) ₂ (89 : 11)	(623–683)	A	2245–783	30.2±1.5	64
NaNO ₃ –Ba(NO ₃) ₂ (94.2 : 5.8)	(623–673)	A	1888–921	30.0±0.8	65
Li ₂ SO ₄ –K ₂ SO ₄ (71.5 : 28.5)	650	A	160	18.9	66
<i>Silver-Iodide</i>					
NaNO ₃ (100)	623	A	49000	47.6	67
KNO ₃ (100)	623	A	12000	40.3	67
KNO ₃ (100)	675	A	5420	39.2	63
KNO ₃ –NaNO ₃ (80 : 20)	673	A	7000	40.5	67
(50 : 50)	623, 648	A	16000, 13000	41.8±0.6	67
KNO ₃ –Ba(NO ₃) ₂ (89 : 11)	(623–663)	A	36848–8982	43.7±2.4	68
NaNO ₃ –Ba(NO ₃) ₂ (94.2 : 5.8)	(623–698)	A	8061–3109	37.9±0.6	69
Li ₂ SO ₄ –K ₂ SO ₄ (71.5 : 28.5)	650	A	1700	31.5	66
<i>Silver-Fluoride</i>					
NaNO ₃ (100)	(586–683)	A	<1 ^a	0.4±0.2	70
KNO ₃ (100)	(619–683)	A	17–15 ^a	7.8±0.1	70
KNO ₃ –NaNO ₃ (33 : 67)	(558–663)	A	≈2 ^a	1.7±0.1	70
(67 : 33)	(557–647)	A	6–5 ^a	0.9±0.1	70
<i>Silver-Cyanide</i>					
NaNO ₃ –KNO ₃ (50 : 50)	(519–599)	A	230000–190000	49.4±3.1	71
<i>Silver-Phosphate</i>					
NaNO ₃ –KNO ₃ (50 : 50)	(524–622)	A	665–579 ^b	23.0±1.7	45
<i>Silver-Nitrite</i>					
NaNO ₃ –KNO ₃ (50 : 50)	(523–623)	A	31–13	7.5±1.0	42

(Table 3 contd.)

GUPTA, VERMA & GAUR : COMPLEX FORMATION IN MOLTEN SALTS :

(Table 3 Contd.)

Complex/Solvent (Composition, Mol %)	Temp. range K	Cell used	K_{11}	$-\Delta A_{11}$	Reference
<i>Silver-Iodate</i> NaNO ₃ - KNO ₃ (50 : 50)	(524 - 622)	A	24 - 26 ^b	8.6 ± 0.9	44
<i>Silver-Molybdate</i> LiNO ₃ (100)	(541 - 622)	A	12 - 10 ^a	5.6 ± 0.1	41
NaNO ₃ (100)	(584 - 690)	A	41 - 26 ^a	10.6 ± 0.1	41
KNO ₃ (100)	(619 - 714)	A	72 - 52 ^a	14.3 ± 0.1	41
LiNO ₃ - NaNO ₃ (60 : 40)	(566 - 650)	A	15 - 13 ^a	6.8 ± 0.3	41
LiNO ₃ - KNO ₃ (43 : 57)	(549 - 653)	A	21 - 16 ^a	7.6 ± 0.3	41
NaNO ₃ - KNO ₃ (50 : 50)	(517 - 646) (524 - 622)	A A	67 - 56 ^a 60 - 44 ^b	11.7 ± 0.3 11.7 ± 0.5	41 46
<i>Silver-Chromate</i> LiNO ₃ (100)	(528 - 600)	A	8 - 7 ^a	4.4 ± 0.1	8
NaNO ₃ (100)	(584 - 673)	A	31 - 25 ^a	9.8 ± 0.2	8
KNO ₃ (100)	(615 - 675)	A	52 - 44 ^a	12.5 ± 0.3	8
LiNO ₃ - NaNO ₃ (60 : 40)	(519 - 610)	A	14 - 12 ^a	5.7 ± 0.4	8
LiNO ₃ - KNO ₃ (43 : 57)	(429 - 595)	A	22 - 15 ^a	6.5 ± 0.5	8
NaNO ₃ - KNO ₃ (50 : 50)	(580 - 695) (524 - 622)	A A	47 - 28 ^a 43 - 35 ^b	10.9 ± 0.5 10.4 ± 0.5	8 43
<i>Silver-Sulphate</i> NaNO ₃ (100)	(594 - 684)	A	≈ 1 ^a	0.9 ± 0.2	41
KNO ₃ (100)	(622 - 715) (636 - 706) (622 - 703)	A A A	13 - 10 ^a 13 - 12 ≈ 13	6.6 ± 0.2 7.2 ± 0.8 7.1 ± 0.4	41 72 73
NaNO ₃ - KNO ₃ (50 : 50)	(526 - 685)	A	4 - 3 ^a	2.3 ± 0.3	41
<i>Silver-Mixed Halide</i> (Cl + Br) NaNO ₃ (100)	711	A	53000	54.8	5
Cl : Br 2 : 1	663, 723	A	414, 278	24.3 ± 0.1	32
Cl : Br 1 : 2	663, 723	A	627, 407	26.6 ± 0.1	32
NaNO ₃ - Ba(NO ₃) ₂ (94.2 : 5.8)	(623 - 673)	A	340250 - 98527	56.6 ± 1.2	31
KNO ₃ - Ba(NO ₃) ₂ (89 : 11)	623, 663 643, 683	A A	889020, 341866 595815, 187920	62.5 ± 0.1 60.6 ± 0.8	74 75
<i>Cadmium-Chloride</i> LiNO ₃ - KNO ₃ (50 : 50)	(413 - 473)	B	1850 - 1200	21.4 ± 0.2	48
(40 : 60)	453	B	1500	21.5	48
(60 : 40)	453	B	1300	21.0	48
(43 : 57)	425	B	1795	20.8	76
NaNO ₃ - KNO ₃ (50 : 50)	527	C	842 ^b	22.5	25
KNO ₃ - Ba(NO ₃) ₂ (87.6 : 12.4)	(568 - 628)	C	600 - 450	23.2 ± 0.4	33
<i>Cadmium-Bromide</i> LiNO ₃ - KNO ₃ (26 : 74)	513	B	2300	26.2	48
(40 : 60)	513	B	2650	26.7	48
(50 : 50)	(444, 513)	B	8000, 3200	27.4 ± 0.2	48
(65 : 35)	513	B	3600	28.1	48
(80 : 20)	513	B	4200	28.7	48
NaNO ₃ (100)	604	C	625	24.3	7
KNO ₃ (100)	631	C	650	25.6	7

(Table 3 Contd.)

(Table 3 Contd.)

Complex/Solvent (Composition, Mol %)	Temp. range K	Cell used	K_{11}	$-\Delta A_{11}$	Reference
$\text{NaNO}_3 - \text{KNO}_3$ (50 : 50)	531	C	1500	25.2	7
	527	C	1983 ^b	26.2	25
	513, 573	B	1520, 990	24.4±0.8	21
	(529-571)	B	1167-810 ^b	24.0±0.2	77
	(53 : 47)				
$\text{NaNO}_3 - \text{LiNO}_3$ (50 : 50)	513	B	2700	26.8	34
$\text{NaNO}_3 - \text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (67 : 33)	533	B	2400	27.4	29
$\text{KNO}_3 - \text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (67 : 33)	(473-553)	B	(5200-2067)	27.6±0.3	29
$\text{KNO}_3 - \text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (87.6 : 12.4)	(568-608)	B	1281-1135	26.9±0.7	30
	568, 628	C	1260, 1000	26.9±0.8	30
<i>Cadmium-Iodide</i>					
$\text{NaNO}_3 - \text{KNO}_3$ (50 : 50)	513, 563	B	5330, 3130	30.0±0.3	21
$\text{KNO}_3 - \text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (87.6 : 12.4)	(568-608)	B	4215-3288	32.3±0.5	35
<i>Lead-Chloride</i>					
$\text{LiNO}_3 - \text{KNO}_3$ (50 : 50)	(433-473)	B	250-205	14.4±0.3	48
$\text{KNO}_3 - \text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (87.6 : 12.4)	(588-628)	C	79-69	13.9±0.2	10
<i>Lead-Bromide</i>					
$\text{NaNO}_3 - \text{KNO}_3$ (53 : 47)	(528-592)	B	199-122 ^b	16.2±0.3	77
	553, 573	B	180, 160	16.6±0.1	52
$(50 : 50)$	(513-573)	B	250-170	16.8±0.1	52
	553, 573	B	200, 175	17.1	52
$\text{LiNO}_3 - \text{KNO}_3$ (50 : 50)	433, 473	B	990, 730	19.3±0.3	48
$\text{KNO}_3 - \text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (87.6 : 12.4)	(568-608)	B	169-137	16.9±0.1	10
<i>Lead-Iodide</i>					
$\text{KNO}_3 - \text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (87.6 : 12.4)	(568-608)	B	3687-2383	31.1±0.1	10
<i>Thallium-Bromide</i>					
$\text{NaNO}_3 - \text{KNO}_3$ (50 : 50)	513	B	31	84	34
$\text{LiNO}_3 - \text{KNO}_3$ (40 : 60)	553	B	56	115	78
<i>Cobalt-Cyanide</i>					
LiCl-KCl (59 : 41)	723	A	435 ^b	26.9	79
<i>Platinum-Bromide</i>					
LiCl-KCl (59 : 41)	723	A	24 ^b	10.6	79
<i>Copper-Cyanide</i>					
LiCl-KCl (59 : 41)	643	A	4372 ^b	36.22	79

* K_{11} in $(\text{mol/mol of solvent})^{-1}$, and ΔA_{11} in kJ mol^{-1} for $Z=5$.

^aBased on quasi-lattice model equation (25).

^bConverted into mol/mol basis from molality unit.

$M_i L_j^{(i-m-j)+}$ may be generalised using the quasi-lattice model equations²⁶⁻²⁸ :

$$K_{11} = Z [\exp(-\Delta A_{11}/RT) - 1] \quad \dots (25)$$

$$K_{12} = \frac{Z-1}{2} \left[\exp(-\Delta A_{12}/RT) - 1 + \frac{\exp(-\Delta A_{12}/RT) - \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta A_{11}}{RT}\right)}{\exp(-\Delta A_{11}/RT) - 1} \right] \quad \dots (26)$$

$$K_{21} = \frac{Z-1}{2} \left[\exp(-\Delta A_{21}/RT) - 1 + \frac{(-\Delta A_{21}/RT) - \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta A_{11}}{RT}\right)}{\exp(-\Delta A_{11}/RT) - 1} \right] \quad \dots (27)$$

Here Z is the quasi-lattice coordination number

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF Ag-X (X=Cl, Br) COMPLEXES EVALUATED BY GRAPHICAL AND COMPUTER METHOD IN NaNO₃-Ba(NO₃)₂

Temp/K	K _{1,1} (Graphical)	K _{1,1} (Computer one-degree fit)
<i>Silver-Chloro complexes</i> (Ref. 28, 60)		
623.2	290 ± 14	292 ± 22
648.2	249 ⁺⁹ ₋₁₂	241 ⁺²⁹ ₋₂₈
673.2	207 ⁺²³ ₋₂₇	198 ⁺²⁰ ₋₁₉
<i>Silver-Bromo complexes</i> (Ref. 28, 65)		
623.2	1888 ⁺⁷⁰ ₋₄₆	1882 ⁺⁴⁵⁰ ₋₄₄₁
648.2	1474 ⁺⁴⁶ ₋₉₂	1290 ⁺¹⁶⁵ ₋₁₇₈
673.2	921 ⁺⁹² ₋₄₆	821 ⁺¹²⁶ ₋₉₆

generally taken³ between 4 to 6, and $\Delta A = \Delta \epsilon - T \Delta S^{int}$ in which $\Delta \epsilon$, the association energy is temperature-independent and $\Delta S^{int} = d(-\Delta A)/dT$ accounts³⁰ for any variation of the internal degrees of freedom of the species taking part in the association processes.

Applicability of the quasi-lattice model containing monovalent and divalent cations and single and polyatomic anions (mixed ligand) has been reported (Table 3); for mixed solvent, ΔA_{mix} is given by temperature independent linear equation³⁰

$$\Delta A_{mix} = Y \Delta A_{AO} + (1-Y) \Delta A_{BO/B'CO_2} \quad \dots (28)$$

(Y is mol fraction of AC)

In some of the systems (Table 3), $\Delta A_{1,1}$ are found to be temperature dependent; non-zero values of $\left(-\frac{d\Delta A}{dT}\right)$ has been ascribed³⁰ to vibrational entropy contributions etc. For Ag-CrO₄ complexes, it is reported³ that ΔA values are temperature-invariant in single solvents, but show a marked dependence in mixtures. This difference in thermodynamic behaviour of ternary and quaternary systems, has led to modification of quasi-lattice formulation using a non-linear equation⁴⁰ for ΔA_{mix} given by

$$\Delta A_{mix} = RT \ln [Y \exp (\Delta A_{AO}/RT) + (1-Y) \exp (\Delta A_{BO/B'CO_2}/RT)] \quad \dots (29)$$

which has been applied to silver-sulphate⁴¹, silver-molybdate⁴¹ and silver-chromate³ complexes in molten nitrates.

Recently, Holmberg *et al*⁴²⁻⁴⁶ examined the applicability of the quasi-lattice model involving polyatomic oxoanion ligands. In these cases also temperature-dependence of the association constants is not described by the quasi-lattice formulation. Relatively small values of ΔA for the formation of AgNO₃⁴² compared to that for chromate⁴³, iodate⁴⁴, phosphate⁴⁵ and molybdate⁴⁶ has been ascribed to

the fact that Ag coordinates to nitrogen⁴²; for others coordination occurs through oxygen.

Solvent effect: Precise data on association constants and specific Helmholtz free energies are available only in relatively fewer single and mixed molten nitrates. The influence of the presence of BC/B'CO₂ in the solvent mixture (AC+BC)/(AC+B'CO₂) on the stability of M-L band has generally been considered in terms of the 'reciprocal coulomb effect'⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹; it results in stabilisation of the pair of oppositely charged ions with the highest charge density. For a system consisting of ions having the same charge, the pairs of smaller ions and pairs of bigger ions of opposite charges will be more stable relative to pairs of ions of mixed size. Considering the change of coulombic energy in the exchange of nearest neighbours taking place in the association reactions of M^{m+} and L^{l-} in solvents AC and BC/B'CO₂,

The energy difference, $\Delta(\Delta U)$ in the two pure solvents would be given by the relation

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(\Delta U) &= \Delta U_{B/B'} - \Delta U_A \\ &= -Ne^2 \left[\frac{1}{r_A + r_L} + \frac{1}{r_{B/B'} + r_{NO_3}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{r_A + r_{NO_3}} - \frac{2}{r_{B/B'} + r_L} \right] \quad \dots (32) \end{aligned}$$

where r_i is the ionic radius, N, the Avogadro's number and e the electronic charge.

For alkali metal nitrates, stability of chloro and bromo complexes in fused alkali nitrates in the order, Li < Na < K < Cs, and that for iodo complexes in the reverse order is observed, iodide being larger than nitrate. The expected trend in mixed nitrate systems relative to single nitrates is shown for Ag-X⁴⁹⁻⁵¹, Cd-X^{7,52} and Pb-X⁵² (X=Cl, Br) complexes in NaNO₃-KNO₃. For Cd-Br complexes, the order of stabilisation is Ba²⁺ > Ca²⁺ > Li⁺, while destabilisation, due to the presence of Na⁺, is observed³⁰ and for Pb-Br complexes¹⁰, the magnitude of destabilisation is in the order Ba²⁺ > Na⁺, while presence of Li⁺ causes stabilisation in KNO₃-BNO₃ (B=Ba²⁺, Ca²⁺, Li⁺, Na⁺), in which both the direction and magnitude of stabilisation are different from those predicted from reciprocal-coulomb effect. This anomalous behaviour also seen in other solvents has been ascribed to the neglect of the long range coulombic^{2,2}, dispersion and polarisation energies^{2,3,4,5,3} and also the difficulty of assigning⁴⁷ an effective ionic radius to the nitrate ion.

For the mixed ligand species, the equilibrium

constants given by

$$\text{equilibrium constant} = \beta / (\beta_{12} \beta_{12}^*)^{1/2} \quad \dots (33)$$

for the exchange reaction $\frac{1}{2} \text{AgCl}_2 + \frac{1}{2} \text{AgBr}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{AgClBr}$ have been evaluated^{5,31}; values are generally higher than the statistical value 2. The stabilisation of the mixed complex over and above the statistical value has been considered to arise due to the electrostatic effect of the exchange of ligands and to the polarizability of the central ion^{5,34}. Also the values of β_{11} and β_{11}^* for single halides evaluated from these (mixed halide) studies generally agree^{5,31} with those independently done for single halide under similar conditions.

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